

137,0359990900848. Quantitative ontology of the Number.
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INTRO

An exhaustive explanation of the origin of the alpha constant and each individual action in its precise calculation have a rather voluminous foundation of theory, or microtheory as part of the Theory of Everything, so here we will limit ourselves to only superficial and approximate explanations, permissible at least for mnemonic purposes. We will give them below after presenting the calculations.

The article was written in Russian, and the author does not vouch for the utmost adequacy of the English translation to all subtle semantic matters, but a mature English-speaking reader will undoubtedly be able to fill in the gaps that arise with the imagination of his own experience.

The value of the task of refuting careless assertions about the randomness of the formation of constants in a series of diverse or even evolving universes of the Multiverse is so global for science that even a timid well-founded doubt about this randomness, sown by some weakly verifiable hypothesis, is of great importance, therefore an accurate calculation of one of the constants, the purpose of which is, at least for a start, to put an end to doubts, to redirect, and not to explode the current scientific discourse, has no less value even with the initial absence of some details in its evidence base.

Here, however, we will glance at many such details.

Calculation or explanation of the genesis of the constant of the fine electromagnetic structure together with all the above-mentioned subtleties has always been fundamentally possible only in metaphysics [1] as a science at the junction of philosophy and physics, and apparently this can explain today some lag of the physics of fundamental constants from the demands of the time - to explain by the untimely oblivion of the science of metaphysics by humanity - but this same consideration automatically excuses physics as a science that has declared its preference for induction over deduction, while metaphysics requires free handling of both with the function guiding the search, delivered to the process by deduction.

Mathematized metaphysics must undoubtedly be a part of physics, and its basic part or beginning, root, and at the same time today it is paradoxically the most under-researched of all its sections.

I

The value of the constant of the fine electromagnetic structure, which was once established, owes its numbers to the interweaving of purely geometric causes, and to bring them together we will need a system of several equations (hereinafter the System).

1. $M_{acc} / (M_1 + M_2 + m_3) = (M_1 + M_2 + m_3) / m_3; M_{acc} < M_D \sqrt{4/\pi} + M_2 < 275; M_1 = 4;$
2. $M_2 = 1/3 E_{ch} = 1/3 ((E_0^2 + E_{2\alpha}^2) / 2)^{1/2}; E_{ch} > (\pi/2)^{1/4}$
3. $M_D = N^D = 243; N = 3, D = 5;$

4. $E_0 = M_0 / M_D = 1,111(1);$
5. $E_{2\alpha} = (M_0 + M_1 + m_3) / M_D; E_{2\alpha} < (4/\pi)^{1/2}$
6. $M_{2\alpha} = M_0 + M_1 + m_3;$
7. $\alpha^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} M_{2\alpha};$

The solution of the system of equations 1 - 7 gives the values for m_3 and other quantities

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_0 &= 270 \\
 m_1 &= 4 \\
 m_3 &= 0,071998180169671733739622635170756... \\
 E_{ch} &= 1,1195210617186043593712990765272... \\
 M_{acc} &= 274,44517186740920652019672232718... \\
 E_{2\alpha} &= 1,1278683052681879495215622330665... \\
 M_{2\alpha} &= 274,071998180169671733739622635170756... \\
 \alpha^{-1} &= 137,035999090084835866869811317585378...
 \end{aligned}$$

with the accuracy provided by the Windows calculator.

The author calculated the constant using this calculator in 2014 manually, while today everyone after reducing the system to the form

8. $(270 + 4 + M_2 + m_3) / (4 + M_2 + m_3) = (4 + M_2 + m_3) / m_3;$
9. $M_2 = 1/3\{[270^2 + (270 + 4 + m_3)^2] / 2\}^{1/2};$

can enter the necessary numbers into any online calculator and get an answer in seconds.

What, in short, does this System say? That if a certain amount of abstract energy, equivalent to the sum of the masses m and M , is supplied to a limited area of a certain volume, then an electron will be born in this volume. In this case, the Compton wavelength of a speculative particle, which we will call a classitron for convenience here and whose wave will determine the parameters of this selected volume by its parameter, will be close in length to the side of a special speculative cube, into which all material points of a stationary electron body, which is not a point in Nature, can be inscribed. For the birth of an electron, it is necessary to achieve a certain energy density in a strictly defined volume, calculated in a special theory, but this volume has long been known to science and owes its size to the classical radius of the electron.

II

Let us add a few preliminary arguments from Argazi's metaphysics (hereinafter referred to as Theory, see below; also see [2] and [3]) before deriving the System. The views of the Theory will be presented here in an approximate presentation with a controlled share of limited correctness.

When starting to study the phenomena of interest to the observer, one should at the very start adopt for oneself a set of main rules, which one will have to use in one's search as logical guidelines for choosing a path and rejecting, at forks, distracting from the search or lengthening the path of directions. (One can assume that in this same multi-vector field it is permissible to look for confirmation of Occam's conclusions and, in principle, note the justified significance of his leading methodological principle, which is considered controversial.) The rules proposed by Argazi on the basis of a metaphysical analysis of the possible connectivity of various physical phenomena in their natural development are endowed by him for physics, which denies metaphysical approaches, with the force of an axiomatic nature. Keeping in mind the understanding of the natural multiplicity of useful rules, including some long-known to scientific logic, the following two are proposed to be considered leading:

The basic rule of m-logic in the descriptive mathematics of the universe.

The complexity of the descriptive mathematics of phenomena increases in the cause-and-effect series of their occurrence. We will call complex phenomena those phenomena that arise by adding several lower-level phenomena into one. Synthetic phenomena are any sum of any phenomena of any level. By addition we will understand any donation of qualities, reflection of regularities or generation of consequences, and not necessarily a complete accounting of all qualities and regularities.

The basic rule tells the observer that the mathematics of the fundamental laws of physics of the root metaphysical level should be simple.

Let us call such a summation of phenomena a phenomenological phase transition, when a new phenomenon generalizes the properties of the old ones that serve as fundamental for it and acquires a new quality that is not described by any of the more fundamental mathematical plots separately or in an incomplete sum, but requires full inclusion in the description of all such plots.

Hierarchical rule of logic.

At the boundary of the phenomenological phase transition, a plot of descriptive mathematics arises, which allows us to abandon the use of fundamental plots in favor of a new one, simplifying the description and calculations, and which is a dialectical consequence of the summation of the fundamental ones. By calling the descriptive mathematics of each phenomenological level an element of the hierarchical organization of the laws of the universe, we come to the conclusion about the need to search for simplifying mathematical plots as an immutable rule in the cognition and subsequent description of the universe.

An example from the most popular: an exhaustive description of the atomic nucleus requires taking into account the rules of behavior of individual neutrons and protons; an exhaustive description of the interaction of two ions requires taking into account the behavior of each electron and nucleus as a whole and does not require knowledge of the behavior of nucleons; molecular biology requires taking into account the behavior of ions of interaction and does not require knowledge of the behavior of all electrons and nuclei.

A useful conclusion for physics would be the conclusion that ideal field theories are redundant. The mathematical complexity of field theories, which (ideally) strive to take into account and use all the laws of the basic plot level when describing phenomena, is inferior in terms of the factor of saving thinking and computing time to the hierarchical approach with the derivation of generalizing laws.

It is further proposed to begin with a description of the background substrate, on which one can begin to study the elementary phenomena placed on it, in particular, the speculative ones, which will

provoke the emergence of those non-random, but which can be defined as quasi-random, strict numerical relationships, which in turn generate physical laws and their constants. Omitting the step-by-step tracking of the logic that led to these or those conclusions, a superficial description of the substrate can be approved for the observer of the alpha constant in the following sounding:

Space-time [4] is a mathematical abstraction. Space-time does not exist in Nature. There is time-space, the organization and ontology of which are described in the works [2], [3] and [5].

Time-space - only in the alpha simplification proposed here - is presented to the observer by two mutually nested three-dimensional branes in two dimensions of their intersection, which are, geometrically speaking, in approximately the same relation as the points of the coordinate axis and the gaps between these points, or - let's take another comparison from philosophy - as something and the other in Hegel [6], which are in constant interaction.

In geometric terms, the branes are endowed with the form of a Clifford 2-torus and in their geometric sum they make up a common 3-sphere of the whole - the space of the universe.

These Clifford tori cannot be considered as mutually nested as a whole, since in that case they would not make up a 3-sphere in total, but should be considered as complementary to each other in the union, with some intersection of global significance for physics discussed below.

There is some difficulty with an adequate geometric representation, for physics, of the result of summing up into a whole of figures, the moments of whose existence under specific observation show some mutual temporal-phase shift, and in metaphysics, a holistic consideration of the form of a parametric space includes four, not two, moments correspondingly with four, not two, interacting Clifford solid tori, which eliminates some incompleteness of a simplified consideration. However, for physics it is most often sufficient to consider two extra tori as being in the imaginary sphere of the semi-hidden geometry of space, complementing the coordinate incompleteness of the solid tori without affecting the accuracy of physical laws, and therefore not requiring more careful attention here.

So, there are two solid tori, their form is Clifford tori, and their sum is a 3-sphere. All three linear geometric dimensions of the 3-sphere, whose cross-similarity is scalar-congruent and which are ideally discrete, i.e. composed of minimal quanta of linear distances of truly singular nature, form the coordinate space of each brane - with only the small subtlety that gaps between coordinate points in the case of a single brane are not mathematically taken into account.

The minimal distances are singular and indivisible, but the lattice structure of the brane system is temporally labile, and calculations on model lattices can only partially follow natural laws.

The time of the universe is absolute, and is in the relation absolute/relative or external timing/duration of local processes with Einstein's time. The duration of processes, which Einstein calls time, is not time and in the cause-and-effect series of physical ontology it receives the role of a secondary consequence, the involvement of which in the case in suitable mathematical practices can be attributed to the category of hierarchically fair and optimal methodological solutions. The time of the universe is ideally discrete, that is, it is calculated by minimal quanta of a truly singular nature, called instants, which are composed of three dimensions of time, constituting the reason for the three-dimensionality of branes and splitting one instant into two three-dimensional (under closer metaphysical consideration, which is not required here, even into four four-dimensional) moments (tick and tock), which can be likened to the relationship of two images in a mirror - internal and external. In this sense, time is six-dimensional, or, more correctly, it is time-space that is six-dimensional (or 4-

dimensional according to Grassmann's rule - for an observer external to time-space and in a simplifying model), and not time itself as the rate of development of all possible movements and transformations in Nature and in the space of the universe itself. According to Grassmann, the fourth dimension is for us the sign of a brane, one of two, observed within its moment of a double instant of the general time-space. Since in one instant of absolute time two branes alternate model-wise, then in this respect the fourth dimension can be considered time, but only in a local sense and as the rate or vector of a single transformation.

In the parametric model with four tori, which is not required by physics, the universe must take into account, however, the formal intersection of two four-dimensional spaces, which has three-dimensionality, that is, operate with five-dimensionality, and this five-dimensionality in turn is a simplification of six-dimensionality, but it turns out that there is no point in delving into these complexities when calculating the constant.

Consonance with string theory [7] can be found in the fact that when separately considering the intersections of two sets of pairwise intersecting four-dimensional spaces, which can or even have to be composed of one pair of four-dimensional spaces of the metaphysics of the constant in question, if we do not take into account temporal shifts within an instant and the laws of their imposition (see, for example, [3]), and these will be two pairs of geometric interaction, as if perpendicular to each other, it will be permissible to speak of two three-dimensional intersections of two pairs of eight-dimensional (in total) half-spaces, that is, in total, of ten-dimensionality. The corresponding mathematical apparatus may exist, but, again, as if perpendicular to the one used by the universe naturally, when it is enough to be satisfied in the parametric space of one's Account with the six-dimensionality of each moment and not to add the missing dimensions, adjusting reality to the method, and not vice versa.

Branes as the internal and external of one phenomenon alternate these two roles at a rate set by absolute time and its two above-described moments, which together constitute one moment of minimal transformation (tick-tock), or minimal transition between two neighboring states of the universe in abstract duration. All changes of all elements of one state transfer all objects to the next state instantly and simultaneously, the speed of signal propagation in this sense does not exist. (In one tick or tock, the universe manages to recalculate all coordinate changes along all three brane coordinate axes, and in this sense, the linear counting speed is equivalent to overcoming the entire radius of the universe in a time much less than the Planck time and which is proposed to be called an instant here.) The speed of movement of objects, including signal carriers, exists in the sense that it is impossible to move between points of absolute coordinates of the universe more than one position of distance in one instant, the minimum distance specified by a single quantum.

We will call a quantum of distance a geoquantum, a quantum of time, that is, an instant, a t-quantum or, in the Russian manner, a tiquantum. The movement of objects, for example, abstract material points (we will consider any manifestation of matter and energy indiscriminately) from which more complex objects are composed, occurs in accordance with the principle of Absolute Relativity of Motion:

The movement of a material point in space occurs by changing the coordinate state in one brane relative to the fixed coordinate system of the second brane, and vice versa, and within one instant two such minimal movements are therefore possible, when two branes - the brane of motion and the brane of coordinates - change roles. Thus, binary objects, represented by bound material points of the

structure in both branes, move in the presence of a motion vector with a maximum speed c equal to half the maximum speed w in the brane, and only free quanta of dark matter, locally not having an antipartner, can theoretically move with double the speed over insignificant distances determined by probability theory. A single impulse of a material point not bound by a partnership can take scalar values only 0 and 1, where $1 = 2c$. The matter of a standard object of the microworld is represented in two branes by two images, or imprints, so its energy or mass is formally doubled, which will later be reflected in many expressions of physics. We will express this energy mass, or emass of the object, in abstract units, called generally quanta or equants, interpreting Einstein's equivalence here as formally as possible. We will also resort to correlating emass with the tabular mass of the electron, taken as a unit.

The mathematical derivation of the value of the constant of the fine electromagnetic structure is connected with the understanding of the congruent identity of the three dimensions in each brane, so that any fully coordinate-defined, pre-defined (here - calculated by the t-machine of changes of the universe, its Counter, ideally and for this area exhaustively) cell of the universal space of one brane formally represents, in a flat Countable space, a cube, although for physics it can represent a completely different figure. The figures of time-space and space-time are geometrically not congruent, but quantitatively, when expressed in any linear or volumetric quanta-measures of conventional physics, they are equal (we speak of an instantaneous cut, a section in time). It will be convenient to resort to the abstraction of the Counter because the calculation by the universe of each subsequent coordinate state of all its material and geometric points is based, firstly, on the data of the previous instantaneous state, and, secondly, is guided by a set of strict rules, the violation of which is impossible and, in fact, for this reason it can be called a calculation that requires a certain power (speed) of the Counter, although formally we are talking about the mechanistic action of Time as an impersonal physical Absolute, as the cause and as the organizer of all elements of any universe and the universe itself in a series of successive ones in their Universe, in the multiverse.

The Multiverse could be called the Metaverse, since its foundations are laid in the metaphysics of the Universe, preceding its applied physics, if the term had not been chartered for online. Time is the dark energy of the universe, and Nature does not offer any other dark energy for physics or astrophysics, time is a cutter, quantizing and complicating the universe in all 6 dimensions (here Kant, as a lover of transcendences, would probably talk about 12 dimensions, but six are enough for physics), a cutter-actor that instantly extends its dimensions and does not need energy, since it itself is energy, which has a state of rest in eternal motion, which can only be slowed down by annihilations.

Metaphysics, in Theory, has its own understanding of the annihilation of private spatial structures in some processes that resemble physical ones, and ultimately reduce the quantization, or the level of discreteness, of spatial dimensions, losing part of their length, but here this topic appears as off-topic and therefore will be omitted.

So, and this is the best comparison, the establishment of multiple images of an object located between two ideal mirrors facing each other does not require energy. The material universe is just a set of images that we consider atomic, and nothing more - the energy of physics has nothing to do with it. That is, the classical energy of surface physics can in a certain sense only slow down time and the growth of the universe, but not speed them up, as in [8], [9], and [10]. There is a limit, and astrophysics can only study downward velocity deviations, but not vice versa. This limit is associated with the value of $2c$ (in each dimension) for the limiting growth rate of the universe. Taking, formally, the physically visible

universe as organized by three (double) dimensions growing at a rate of $2c$ at an age of 13.75 billion light years, we obtain, according to the Pythagorean theorem, an estimate of 47.63 m.s.l. for the universal radius, the decrease of which to 46 can be explained by annihilations of matter or in black holes, or in other ways throughout the existence of the universal whole - if we discard versions with errors in determining the age. It should be remembered, however, that this is not a scientific, but only a vulgar geometric estimate of the radius.

The calculated cubic - for the brane observer - cell of any size, in which the Counter is preparing to place some material body, is not obliged, as noted above, to contain precisely a cubic body, and yet when placing in it an observed object of a different shape, when this object is entirely inscribed in the observed cell, all material points of the cell must be coordinately pre-determined, since the cell in this case represents a local coordinate system for placing the material points of the body, and it is in this requirement that we find the primary reason for establishing a certain value for the constant alpha.

Let us assume that two three-dimensional branes as independent objects have between themselves, from a mathematical point of view, a natural intersection formally being a two-dimensional object, conditionally a plane. This plane is represented by both two-dimensional quanta-coordinates of the first kind, its conditionally positive points, and of the second kind, its conditionally negative points, conditional gaps between the points of the first brane. Since one and every instant of absolute time contains one such intersection, and the material world must acquire its physical appearance as something coordinately completely determined, which is impossible in the depths of each brane outside the subspace of their intersection, establishing in itself the required pre-determination, then the physical world with its space-time appears (at every instant) to the time-spaces themselves or to their observers as truly flat and, as was said above, in the visible space-time of physics is not flat, having other forms and inscribed shapes.

III

An electron at rest forms an ideal spherical body from its material points, and this body is triple in accordance with the ontology of its synthesis of the universe (it can also be imagined as a body of rotation, which is physically indisputable), and the electron - which is not necessary for other particles - is composed of three quantitatively equal parts, and thirdly, for time-space the electron is a flat figure, that is, geometrically, a circle, and the Counter calculates it - as spherically flat for each of the components of the universal superposition of branes - separately and moment by moment. We can talk about a small spherical body (pre-wave, in particular - within the limits established by its classical radius), imagining it as a circle rotating on the axis of the diameter, drawing a ball in 3-space, and this idea will prove convenient in approaches to calculation.

For certain reasons, the classical radius of the electron in metaphysics is the classical diameter of the electron. As a reason acceptable for physics, we use the fact that in metaphysics the entire charge of an electron is formed in its classical sphere, and not in its volume, although this fact in the cause-and-effect series of the metaphysics of the electron is in itself no more than one of the side effects. Accordingly, the energy index mc^2 is achieved for such a charged body at a halved value of the classical radius of physics. It is also important to specially consider the so-called wave body of particles at rest, the radius of which is tied to the Compton wavelength of the particle (or virtual particle, unstable associate, etc.), and time is devoted to this consideration in the Theory, here we will only mention this factor without a worthy analysis as not affecting the accuracy or nature of the calculations, only noting

its following ontological importance in the formation of the constant as a necessary (not sufficient) condition:

The instantaneous value of the diameter of the wave body of a physical object in physical space is with the length of the side of the cube of the Countable parametric space, capable of inscribing this body completely, in a ratio equal to or greater than the ratio of the diameter of the circle describing the square of the parametric section of the cube to the length of the side of this square.

Of course, when speaking of a physical object, we do not mean a random accumulation of material points, but we mean a certain structure endowed with an independent existence.

This observation, this one of the mentioned rules of the Law of Organization of Masses (LOM) of the universe, the projective-wave rule, is a consequence of the fact that the maximum distances between the points of the described sections are determined by the diagonal, and not by the side of the square, and the wave body of a physical object at the same time requires for itself a spherical, and not a cubic arrangement, formally provided by the Countable space, and even for objects of the microworld at rest in the absence of rotation, since the very structure of the time-space containing them is labile, that is, in a certain sense, we can imagine the wave section as a figure of rotation of a parametric square with a side equal to the Compton wavelength, in its own plane around its center. This figure will be composed by superimposing many snapshots of a square rotating, uniformly or oscillatingly. The lability of the lattice structure of the space containing the objects is connected with pointwise chaotic fibrillations relative to each other, even at rest, not only of branes and embedded objects, but also of the branes themselves among themselves. The quantum spatial field of branes is itself composed of separate fields of all their own material points, just as the wave functions of objects (more strictly speaking, their geo-potentials) are summed up at infinity in order to form the wave function of the whole. Space in metaphysics is an immanent external for the internal material structure of any object, this external is its personal external, its own quantum field and its contribution to the general field in full accordance with how Hegel predicted (3). Objects are non-local, their physical influence is limited by the dimensions of the containing universe, their trains are volumetrically equal to the universe, the universe is the sum of its objects, the sum of the trains makes up the entire space of the universe, and the popular entanglement of particles is a consequence of these circumstances. All particles are entangled to some extent in one common whole, but some are entangled more entangled.

Since all material points of branes move freely, relatively freely or limitedly freely in each brane (integrally - in the 3-sphere) at each instant of observation, the exact form of any local space formed by the superposition of their moving quantum trails also changes (which is noted in Einstein's General Theory of Relativity). Since this form is determined non-locally by all material m-points of the entire space of the universe, since their trails are non-local, it becomes impossible for a t-machine to operate at a speed that is capable of taking into account all changes in the whole generated by changes in those parts that are generated in turn by locally specified limitations of this same speed. A t-machine capable of disputing this would offer an infinite speed of light for its universe - or would work in a universe of a larger number of dimensions, in which the parametric universe of the Count is only one of the sections, which is not welcomed by the metaphysics of the Theory and Occam's razor. Thus, the Counter, for the purpose of coordinate re-definition of a certain selected spatial region in its dynamics, and not stationary, is left to be guided by taking into account its main limiting parameter - the maximum distance between the lattice points. This introduces into the geometry of physics the natural sphericity

of the microcosm of the localization of the microworld object even without imposing conditions for its own rotation, and the observer is faced with the fact of the need to take into account the parameters of the contact spheres in his hypotheses.

In the attached Glossary** one can find some justifications for the terminology proposed below and some accompanying explanations of the consequences of the choice of such terminology or the benefit of its application for the physics of the constant under study.

The sections of the contact spheres of the embedding of the calculated objects of the universe should be considered figures of coaxial rotation of two parametric squares relative to each other, since such squares of each brane are calculated by the t-machine singly and independently and without regard to whether some temporal regularity is attached to the random changes in the positions of such squares relative to each other.

Only objects of the microworld with masses not exceeding the mass of the Planck body can serve as calculated objects. Large objects are generated by the interaction of conditional orbitals of geofields of their calculated objects as elements of the whole, and sometimes by complementary interaction with geofields of the universe belonging to sources outside the contour of physical localization of the observed object. Geometrically, each isolated train of a single parametric m-point shows for time-space a certain cone-shaped embedding in the brane solid Clifford torus with filling of the solid torus with spatial quanta of other trails, and the space of the universal whole is (in a simplified model) an instantaneous interaction of two Clifford solid tori, positive and negative, with the formation of a 3-sphere, while the calculation by the Counter of distances between m-points of different branes gives the physical form of the objects of observation three-dimensionality, absent in the half-spaces of flat intersection. Three-dimensionality arises only in the interaction of two branes as a new relation, absent in two flat separately isolated worlds. Thus, two types of rotation are revealed to the observer – material and spatial – and these two types of rotation do not need synchronization, and each of them is responsible for the existence of one of the two types of spheres containing objects of the microworld. The second of these types, through some of its simple consequences, determines the spin. In this case, it is worth highlighting the following circumstances accompanying rotations first of all. The real number of geophysical points, or coordinate places, containing an object of flat space, which is a square in the Counting (parametric) space of the t-machine, must coincide with the number of the same points in physical space; the counter cannot provide greater speed. The exact form of the spatial figure, transcendental to the square in physical space, is of no importance. Thus, the diameter of a flat spherical figure of physics $\pi d^2/4$ will exceed the length of the side of the corresponding parametric square d^2 by $\sqrt{4/\pi}$ times.

Accordingly, the wave body with its diametrically-diagonal excess of the length of the side of the square by $\sqrt{2}$ times must be compressed, for Counting purposes, by $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ time – since $\sqrt{2}/\sqrt{4/\pi} = \sqrt{\pi/2}$. If there is a task to provide the Counter with the volume of space that it can cope with during the calculation, ensuring the independent existence of the object, the constant $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ or the constant associated with it, in other calculations, $(\pi/2)^{1/4} = 1.1195151\dots$ will also have significance in a broader sense as linking the mass-energy content of any spherical region – the physical, or contact, sphere – with the permissible mass-energy content of the physical object inscribed (in a smaller calculation sphere, packing, reaction sphere) in this region of the same linear (dictated by the diameters) density. We are talking about an object capable of acquiring structure and independence, not about a chaotized portion

of energy; and among other things, the constant determines the lower limit for the ratio of the radius of the wave body/the radius of the calculated spherical body of the physical object (in the microworld). This rule of the LOM can be formulated for radii or diameters D in the following form:

The radius of the cross-section of the packing space, or the calculated sphere, of an independent physical object of the microworld is necessarily connected with the radius of the cross-section of the physical (contact) sphere of space of the same linear material density, which exceeds it, in which the corporeal synthesis of this object can be organized, by a ratio determined by the constant of the first pre-projection $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ and providing the minimum requirement for the possibility of synthesis.

$$10. D_{ph} \geq D_{es} \sqrt{\pi/2}$$

In other words, if the necessary condition determined by the constant is met, and in the presence of all other necessary conditions of the LOM for the final sufficiency, the birth, or synthesis, of a new particle becomes possible in a given region of space. At the same time, the presence of the required amount of energy mass in the physical sphere, as we see, does not yet allow us to hope for the synthesis of a particle, and only an excess of this e-mass by $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ times (an increase in energy density) allows hope to be born. Let us recall that we are talking about the condition "from below", an excess of the dictated density requirements is welcomed.

So, we are talking about the minimum requirement. What do the incomprehensible quirks of the Universal Counter with some of the restrictions imposed by them, which have an exact numerical expression, mean for physics? The requirement discussed above, for example, is applied, firstly, to the contact distance to the center of the target, specified by the observed physical sphere, which should be taken into account by the observer directing the energy beam to the target, about the interaction cross-section, and, secondly, it is applicable to the assessment of the density of energy absorbed by the target required for the experiment.

What is the calculated spot, the calculated sphere of matter organization? This is the packing volume (for time-space – the area of a spot, section), within which all material points of the corporeal structure of the synthesized object are located at rest. The quanta of its e-mass (which can be initially composed of elements of different discrete nature – in the classics, for example, quarks, gluons, partons, etc. – and this does not matter, the count can be conducted in conditional equanta), whatever they may be, all without exception are located in the volume of a certain section, which is required by the structure of the object itself. Thus, for example, the structural arrangement of the electron requires its physical organization strictly within the boundaries set by its classical radius, which is 137 times smaller than the reduced Compton wavelength of the electron $L_0/2\pi$ (in metaphysics – 274 times), and the structure of the photon occupies (conditionally: conditionally not massless) the entire wave volume outlined by such a length, that is, not all particles are packed in volumes quantitatively close to their wave body. At the same time, the purely speculative mono-particle 243, about which we will talk a lot, places its spherical body within the boundaries outlined precisely with the help of the classical radius of the electron, corresponding to the Compton wavelength of the also purely speculative α^{-1} -particle.

In some cases, which include the case of the classitron, the calculated capacity of the parametric space, corresponding to the speed of the Counter, begins to be insufficient for the complete coordinate completion of the definition of the wave body of the object (the case of light particles; the range of true

lepton masses in metaphysics is limited from above by the mass of the classitron $2\alpha^{-1}$). Under the condition, let us recall, that for the placement of a certain object we need a completely definite local space. Thus, the complete completion of the definition of the local space for the wave body of the classitron (also a purely speculative particle) is possible with a decrease in the area of the "wave cross-section" of at least $\pi/2$ times - only in this case the number of coordinate points of the local spherical space of physics, as we have already noted, will not exceed the number of Counting points of the parametric space allowed by the speed of the Counter (we are talking about the ratio of the areas of the circle/square - for the reaction (calculation, Counting) sphere, - equal to one).

That is, a classitron with a relative mass of $2\alpha^{-1}$ (in parametric time-space with its speed of light of $2c$, such a particle has the necessary Compton wavelength, equal to the wavelength of the conditional classitron-137 of physical space) requires for itself (if the condition of speculative synthesis is its full-weight placement in precisely such a large volume) a cross-section of the accommodating calculation body at least $\pi/2$ times smaller than that provided to it by the contact sphere of physical space, and a particle with a mass of 243, for example, another $1.127868...^2$ times smaller, as it requires less calculation time.

Taking the Counting Cross Section of particle 243 to be $\pi/2$ times smaller than that provided by its contact body, we come to the conclusion that it is necessary to decrease the diameter of this cross section by $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ times, i.e. to increase the energy content of the observed contact cell of such a particle by no less than $(\pi/2)^{1/2}$ times (condition (2) of the System: $E_{ch}^2 > (\pi/2)^{1/2}$) compared to the energy mass of 243 (the same calculation sphere is required by an electron for own synthesis as a triple, not a monobody, according to condition (3) of the System; for more details, see below).

An electron with the relative mass of a triple body, conventionally taken as 1, can be synthesized in a certain strictly defined volume only in the presence of a cluster of quanta, for some reason located in this volume, with a total mass of no less than $243 * 1.253314... = 243\sqrt{\pi/2}$. The same condition applies to the mass-energy density of the same Counting Volume of monobodies 243 times more massive. In the case of a triple body of the electron type, we will need an increase in the amount of unstructured mass-energy in this volume to $243 * \sqrt{\pi/2}$ conventional units of emass. And under these conditions, the synthesis of an electron with the displacement of the excess energy that has become garbage away from the reaction volume becomes possible - or its use in the process of some page synthesis that enhances the Le Chatelier factors.

A speculative spherical monoparticle with a conventional mass of 243 (that is, with some speculative mass-energy of 243) or a triple particle with an electron mass 243 times smaller can be fully synthesized by the Counter of the universe in volumes of physical space no larger than those that correspond to the calculated body of an abstract associate of monoparticles with a total energy mass of $243 * (4/\pi)^{1/2}$. This calculated body, by a certain coincidence, is close in linear packing dimensions to the calculated body of the $2\alpha^{-1}$ parametric space classitron, and such coincidences begin to form a general list of quasi-random conditions, the sum of which will determine the future value of the alpha constant and the magnitude of the classical radius of the electron along with the mass of the latter.

Let us note in the margins that the ratio $\sqrt{2}$ of the diagonal of the parametric square of the $2\alpha^{-1}$ particle to its side is close in the conditions under consideration to the product $E_{2\alpha}E_{ch}^2$, where $E_{2\alpha}$ is close in this case to the ratio of the diameter of the packing (calculated) sphere to the side of the parametric square, and E_{ch}^2 is close to the ratio of the diameter of the wave body before its physical compression to

the diameter of the packing sphere, which is a banal remark that may not be immediately noticed, since this closeness is ensured not by the value of $E_{2\alpha}$ itself, but by its closeness to the value of $(4/\pi)^{1/2}$, which geometrically combines in the product $E_{2\alpha}(\pi/2)^{1/2}$ the diameters of the calculated circle and circle which including the square.

Also of the utmost importance is the rule from the above-mentioned LOM, which prescribes to the law of growth of unit masses not exceeding the mass of the classitron $2\alpha^{-1}$ to ensure, in the process of energy supply to the observed volume, a linear growth relative to the procedural timing (and not the quantity) of the energy supplied uniformly, and a quadratic growth in the case of the object exceeding the classical indicator: quadratic objects in this sense absorb more energy per unit time and achieve larger masses. If the mass of the classitron $2\alpha^{-1}$ is here called metaclassical in the interests of categorical brevity, then the growth rule of LOM, also in its brief form, can be formulated as follows:

- Substantive objects of the microworld with supercritical masses exceeding the metaclassical, show, under equal conditions of transformation into heavier objects of any target mass, a relative rate of instantaneous mass growth showing a quadratic value in comparison with the linear instantaneous rate of mass growth of objects with subcritical masses, "premeta-masses".

If the wave body of objects is called a volume whose diametrical size $\sqrt{2}$ is determined by the Compton length 1 of the corresponding wave of *parametric* time-space, this rule can be reformulated as:

- An independent object of the microworld with a subcritical value of the Compton wavelength, smaller than the metaclassical one, shows, under equal conditions of transformations into heavier objects of any target mass, a relative rate of instantaneous growth showing a quadratic value in comparison with the linear rate of instantaneous growth of the mass of an object with a supercritical wavelength, which determines the dimensions of its wave body at rest.

Obviously, we are talking about bodies whose growth and mass growth factors are limited by the target value of the Compton wavelength of the heavy goal of the growth process, and not by some sliding indicators. A distant, and much more complex, analogy can be considered the requirement of filling the first orbitals of an atom with electrons - until the primary level is filled, Nature will not allow the next one to be filled. Seeing in both phenomena the manifestations of the principle of economy of thinking, we can formulate as a consequence the principle of how the quadratic growth of particles or associates inherits the rules of their primary linear growth at the moment of exhaustion of the potential of the latter.

Thus, to test this rule, it is necessary to ensure a strictly uniform supply of excess energy to the observed object, capable of absorbing this energy with transformation into a heavier object, and to make sure that, under equal conditions, when an independent object exceeds the mass of the classitron $2\alpha^{-1}$, the rate of growth of its mass will become quadratic in relation to the rate of growth of its own mass until the moment the object reaches the mass of the classitron. In physics, this rule is not obvious and difficult to verify, if at all, but plays a crucial role in metaphysics and in the ontology of mass organization, being part of the LOM.

The last object of the microworld that shows a quadratic rate of mass growth according to the LOM growth rule is the Planck body, and then the metaphysical laws of mass growth no longer apply.

This rule could be formulated in the ideology of proportionality of the growth of supercritical masses to the cross-sectional area of the observed cell, if the growth of subcritical masses in the same

cell is recorded by the observer as linear, however, in conditions when the observed cell is often linked in size to the wave body of the object, which changes with the growth of its mass, an unnecessary, although easily taken into account mathematically, uncertainty is introduced into the rule. In addition, in metaphysics, time is recognized as the culprit of geometric relationships, and the temporal, or rate-base, version of definitions seems ontologically more rigorous, all other things being equal.

In any case, when placing particles of subcritical and supercritical masses in two intentionally identical Counting Volumes, the former – when fed into the volumes with the same and excess energy flow in both cases – will show a quadratic rate of mass growth in comparison with the latter; let us repeat: if such growth is justified at all.

IV

The circle inscribed in the square of the flat section of the cubic cell of each brane differs from it by an area reduced by $4/\pi$ (1.273239544...) times, allowing its linear filling with pre-determined material quanta (m-quanta, in observation – speculative) in an amount $\sqrt{4/\pi} - 1.128379167...$ – times smaller. This allows the quantum pump aimed at organizing a $2\alpha^{-1}$ -associate in the cell to hope to achieve by pumping the cubic cell with energy precisely such an excess of its energy capacity in comparison with the capacity of the circle inscribed in the square (the excess will be determined by the limit of 274.196... for the linear form of filling the circle with a conventional mass of 243). In the System above, the speculative and relative mass of such a circle, the total mass of its conditional m-quanta (or mass) was mentioned earlier. Let us repeat the publication of the System with some explanations.

$$11. \quad M_{\text{ass}} / (M_1 + M_2 + m_3) = (M_1 + M_2 + m_3) / m_3 \quad (\text{spin-wave, or cascade, condition}),$$

where $M_{\text{ass}} < M_{2\alpha} + E_{2\alpha} / 3 < 243\sqrt{4/\pi} + E_{2\alpha} / 3 < 275$ – the conditional and relative mass-energy (emass) of a virtually material associate, which is the fruit of the speculative pumping of the observed cell of space with speculative mass-energy in the form of its individual quanta; m_3 is an unknown component of mass-energy as a by-product of the quantum pump operation, the energy mass of which reaches its value at the moment of reaching the final plateau of temporary stability during the formation of the $2\alpha_{-1}$ particle; M_1 is a number approaching 4 as the last integer by means of which the mass of 270 is exceeded before the linear limit of subcritical saturation of the cell $243*\sqrt{4/\pi}$, and this number got into the System only for this reason; the equating of the two proportions is dictated by one of the rules (see below), which are not considered here in all detail, characteristic of the moment of birth of ideal triple bodies, the rules of the Law of Mass Organization (LOM) from Argazi's cosmology.

$$12. \quad M_2 = 1/3 E_{\text{ch}} = 1/3 ((E_0^2 + E_{2\alpha}^2) / 2)^{1/2} \quad (\text{reaction-resonance condition}),$$

where M_2 is the mass of the associate, a kind of resonance interacting with the triumvirate of identical parton masses of the M_{ass} at the end of the alpha process, observed as a new associate $3k_{\text{new}}*M_{\text{ass}}$ with cross-links of new stability according to the saturation limit of the coordinately pre-defined regions by the notional Counter. (The links called cross-links here arise when the neighboring elements of the emerging new complex structure interact with individual elements of the neighbors' structure due to their certain unsaturation relative to this new potential provided by the LOM). For certain reasons, triple associates often have additional stability explained by the LOM, and, in addition,

when the mass of the classitron is exceeded, they grow quadratically relative to the timing of the process from start to finish, and not linearly like the classitron itself - the excess of the absorbed mass in quadratic structures becomes a kind of glue from the second dimension, holding together linear structures. By allusion, we can call this glue speculative gluons.

In this case, all structural elements of the associate have masses (more precisely, the linear part of the associated emasses, related to their starting mass M_{01} by the coefficient E_{ch}), determined by the coefficient E_{ch} . In particular, a third of the electron mass M_e , taken here as a unit, would have a temporary mass of $1/3(M_e * E_{ch})$ in such a quantum soup, being one of the components of the growing (speculative) associate. Thus, the quantum pumping's soup at the moment of reaching the last plateau of stability, described by expression (11), will be three structurally connected soup bones $M_4 = (270 + 4 + M_2 + m_3)E_{ch}$, surrounded in the quantum broth by ingredients with masses $M_{01} * E_{ch}$ – but the linear parton $M_{2\alpha}$ itself will also be temporarily composed of similar elements $M_x * E_{ch}$.

Eventually, after reaching the alpha plateau of stability and fulfilling all the conditions of the System, the quantum soup of the triple cell will potentially acquire the mass of $3E_{2\alpha}M_{2\alpha}$ and then $3*243(4/\pi)$, completing the phase transition, but by this point a number of changes may have occurred with its ingredients. Thus, expression (11) could be represented in a form similar to

$$13. \quad 3E_{ch}[M_{ass} / (M_1 + M_2 + m_3)] = 3E_{ch}[(M_1 + M_2 + m_3) / m_3],$$

if it were not for its mathematical degeneracy before the cancellation of factors. Operating with the total masses of partons, it should be noted that the part of the total energy content of the cell, distinguished by the mass $M_0 * E_{ch}^2 = 243 * 1.119521...^2$, upon reaching the alpha plateau, enters into an associate with the mass $2_{\alpha-1}E_{ch}$ and is adjacent to a grain of small masses $M_1 * E_{ch}$, if in this case M_1 is taken to be the linear component of the atomic mass of each object, and $M_1 * E_{ch}$ is the atomic mass itself in the quadratic quantum soup, while, historically speaking, $M_1 = M_0 * E_{ch}$. Below, the reasons for this will be considered less briefly.

$$14. \quad M_D = N^D = 243; N=3, D=5 \quad (3\text{-parton-5-dimensional condition}),$$

where N is the number of structural partons of a complex particle, D is the number of time-space dimensions involved in the calculation; M_D shows how many times the calculated mass of a coordinately extended object decreases when placed in the same Counting cell as the compared mono-object, if the mono-object is replaced by a poly-partonic object - due to the limitations imposed by the Counter speed and the need to perform calculations, adding an additional cybernetic dimension to the process when placing material points of the structure in several partonic cells. (In this case, it is not important how these partons differ from each other, for example, internal spins that retain their value for some time.)

Where do the six parametric dimensions come from if the Counting is performed separately for two three-dimensional spaces? This can be explained even in a simplified alpha model. The position of any material point is determined in the three-dimensional half-space of its placement. However, within the framework of one instant, the coordinate locations of this half-space itself in relation to the second half-space also undergo a three-dimensional change. Therefore, the number of counting dimensions still

remains equal to six, and therefore we are later faced with the need to take into account two types of systemic motion of the object at rest and its local space.

From the six calculated, when determining the number of real, dimensions of the parametric space - when calculating the number D - one imaginary is subtracted when there is no need to take it into account in the Counting process due to the complete synchronization of two of the six counting parameters for some reason that makes the dual calculus degenerate. In the case of an electron, such a reason will be the emergence, as a new parameter degenerating duality, of a rigid structural bi-distance between the parametric planes of the imprints of the bi-matter of the object in two interacting branes (in the absence of such conditions for the five remaining dimensions of the Account). The imprints are separated in the parametrics like ideal plates of a capacitor, and the separation distance is formed by ideally mutually nested dimensions of two signs. Sic: classical time of physics is not included in the considered list of dimensions formed by the parameters of the instant.

$$15. E_{0\alpha} = M_0 / M_D = 1.111(1) \quad (\text{the constant of the starting plateau of stability, or configuration coefficient}),$$

where $E_{0\alpha}$ is the starting condition for calculating the relative growth of the linear component of the total pump energy, related to the mass-energy of the intermediate plateau of stability of the forming speculative associate $270E_{0\alpha}$, stabilizing itself by strong internal parton bonds due to the subordination to the Law of mass organization and due to the unique basis of partons of the 270, 27 and 3 type and their ratios of the 300/30/3 type to correspond to this subordination, which should be discussed additionally. (Or it can become the final condition for the inverse process of decay of the triple $3x2\alpha-1$ particle (or its particle $3*243*E_{2\alpha}^2$) with the final goal of the plateau of stability $3M_0$, where $M_0 = 270$; metaphysics does not require precise knowledge of the alternation of physical processes and often even of their direction or conditions of reversibility, but establishes from a number of possible ones only the inevitable quantitative relationships for them by considering virtual processes in thought experiments that emphasize the general in the particular.)

$$16. E_{2\alpha} = (M_0 + M_1 + m_3) / MD \quad (\text{alpha-preprojection constant}),$$

where the value of the constant $E_{2\alpha}$ is the final condition for the relative growth of the linear component of the partonic energy of the virtual pumping, corresponding to the plateau of formation of the $3x2\alpha^{-1}$ particle.

$$17. M_{2\alpha} = M_0 + M_1 + m_3 = \alpha^{-1}w/c, \quad (\text{final mass of the alpha parton, linear contribution}),$$

where $M_{2\alpha}$ is the final mass-energy of pumping (linear contribution) to the alpha associate during the operation of the quantum pump in the cell at the time of formation of the $(\alpha^{-1}w/c)$ particle; c is the speed of light; $w = 2c$ is the maximum speed of a single movement of a material point in the universe, the "world" speed.

$$18. M_\alpha = \frac{1}{2} M_{2\alpha} = \alpha^{-1},$$

where $M_{2\alpha}$ is the relative linear mass-energy of a virtual cubic particle of parametric space as a result of the operation of a speculative quantum pump, which in physics receives a halved value (of α^{-1}), in its dimensionless form entered physics as a constant, since it forms the relationship between the mass and the Compton wavelength of an electron.

The halving of $M_{2\alpha}$ occurs because of the geometric doubling of the distances calculated for the System in the bi-brane time-space (in physical space the observer encounters only the projection of this space into its physics) and because of the formal doubling of the speed of light in such time-spaces, which is considered in more detail in the main body of Argazi's metaphysics, while in physical space the dimensions of any cell associated with Compton wavelengths are linearly halved. As a result, formally speaking, the calculation is carried out for the volumetric parameters of a body of half the mass if we want to preserve the cell size determined by the Compton wavelength of the $2_{\alpha-1}$ particle in the bi-brane time-space (where $w = 2c$), and not in physical space, and only such a size supports the necessary calculations, since we are considering the metaphysics of the processes that underlie future physics directly in the process of its origin, and not their physics itself.

Filling of the flat (sic: flat only in parametric space) section of observation cells with single quantum masses with the growth of their sum in the controlled process of the so-called linear growth of the cell contents will occur "linearly" in the sense of conformity with the growth of the different fixed radii of packing cells observed in different compared experiments for the masses, and not with the growth of the fixed areas (in search of an analogy it is useful to recall a similar rule for the masses of black holes, which has a very indirect relation to this rule). Filling of the flat section of packing, or calculation, cells with supercritical density, however, in the same sense will occur quadratically, proportionally to the difference in the observed areas, since we are considering processes on scales far from comparison with the density indicators of black holes of similar volume. Sic: we are not talking now about wave bodies that are compressed, in relation to the growth of the host masses, always linearly-radially, here we are talking about speculative processes.

In general, the formula for calculating the constant of the fine electromagnetic structure can be written as

$$19. \alpha^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} N^D * T_2,$$

where $T_2 = E_{2\alpha}$ is the coefficient of the secondary alpha-preprojection, which matches the flat parametric geometry of the Counter of the universe with the geometry of the physics of electron synthesis, using corrections; N is the number of partons in the composite body of the electron of the universe; D is the number of real spatial (geo-) dimensions of the Account of its t-machine, not associated with "physical time". The coefficient of the primary alpha-preprojection can be considered the above-considered relationship $\sqrt{4/\pi}$, which has a geometric origin.

The number of temporal moments in one instant of time-space is three, in accordance with the number of spatial dimensions of the brane, calculated by the Counter independently, but each of the moments is divided into two by a special sign - we can call this the direction of the instantaneous motion of the cutter of time-absolute, quantizing the universal body, distinguishing two branes - and the number of dimensions in the meaning of the Account becomes equal to six. However, the sixth

dimension (- Z, for example, in the Euclidean analogy) for structured masses can become imaginary, since it is placed as if in an imaginary hemisphere of such a restricted time-space of the Account (in global metaphysics this is reflected in a broader sense, the sixth dimension comes to it from the ontological Whole-measure of physical things, the non-discrete Whole, from the Whole-transcendence - at the choice of categorization professionals) and does not take away computer time from the t-machine of the universe for its every-instant recalculation.

Further, according to the Law of organization of masses, including in relation to this case, a virtual particle with an emass of 270 has a special stability in the indicated conditions, and even more so - a triumvirate of partons based on it with an emass of 810 or $3 \cdot 270$. In Nature such particles may not be noticed due to their insignificant lifetime, but in the hidden processes of metaphysics and especially the speculative metaphysics of the "critical mind" their existence is in demand. In principle, when considering the process of decay of infiltrates of several neighboring cells of the classitron pumped with energy to the index $243 \cdot E_{2\alpha}^2$, one can study the intermediate processes of the general scheme

$$20. \quad 3 \cdot 243 \cdot E_{2\alpha}^2 \rightarrow 3 \cdot 270 \cdot E_{ch} + \Delta m,$$

where the decay leads to the intermediate formation of resonance particles with masses $m_{mid} = m_1 \cdot E_{ch} = m_0 \cdot E_{ch2}$, and the structural transformation of the linear start $3 \cdot 243 \cdot E_{2\alpha}$ to the energetically (or structurally) favorable target $3 \cdot 270$ provokes decay. But the choice of virtual schemes will not affect the accuracy of the calculation, given that the schemes themselves in Nature will be even more complex or diverse, and with the tools of metaphysics it is ideologically too early to claim their exact guessing, which will make senseless the attempts of observers to seem more rigorous. The interweaving of subtle instantaneous processes in the integral process of electron synthesis may turn out to be generally not subject to division by physics according to the criteria of early, late, primary, secondary, synchronous or simultaneous, but the quantitative relationships established by metaphysics through a comparative analysis of the influences of such process determinants as different types of geometries cannot be different due to the simplicity of the basis mathematizing these geometries, which does not allow numerical variability.

V

The spin-wave rule of LOM, reflected by condition (1) of the System, states:

The interaction of three particles, leading to their unification or fusion into a new particle, is maximally facilitated by such a coordination of their angular momenta, when the Compton wavelength of their total rest mass is shorter than the Compton wavelength of the total mass of the two smaller particles in the same ratio in which the wavelength of the total mass of the two smaller particles is shorter than the wavelength of the smaller of the three particles.

In view of the indisputable connection of the masses of particles with their Compton wavelengths, the spin-wave rule can be reformulated as follows:

The interaction of three particles leading to their unification or fusion into a new particle is maximally facilitated by such a coordination of their orbital angular momenta that their total rest mass exceeds the total rest mass of the two smaller particles in the same ratio in which the total mass of the two smaller particles exceeds the mass of the smaller of the three particles:

$$21. (m_1 + m_2 + m_3) / (m_2 + m_3) = (m_2 + m_3) / m_3$$

$$22. L_{m1,2,3} / L_{m2,3} = L_{m2,3} / L_{m3} ;$$

We have used the term "particle" here in a general way; masses can be complex, composite, can be random, temporary or instantaneous associates; for metaphysics, unlike the physics of processes, this is of no importance. And we are talking about a kind of moment of capture by a quantum octopus of a new small victim to increase its mass, and subsequently the heavier organism of the associate can undergo restructuring using other optimizing proportions.

In the case of inclusion of relatively independent partons in the composition of a heavier associate, one should speak not of wave, but of packing bodies of these partons.

The interaction of three particles, leading to their unification or fusion into a new particle, is maximally facilitated with such coordination of their angular momenta, when the radius of the packing sphere of their total rest mass is smaller than the radius of the packing sphere of the total mass of two smaller particles in the same ratio in which the radius of the sphere of the total mass of two smaller particles is smaller than the radius of the sphere of the smaller of the three particles.

VI

The constituent particles of the supercritical "over-bialphamass" $\propto 2\alpha^{-1}$, according to the LOM and the growth rule, no longer obey the laws of linear growth during energy pumping of their cells, and grow quadratically in comparison with the indicators demonstrated by mono-cells - both instantaneously and eventually reaching a greater specific mass. In this regard, the mass of the triumvirate, for example, reaching a plateau of stability, reaches an instantaneous value of $3 \cdot 243 \cdot 1.11(1)^2 = 900$ and then the growth continues according to the aforementioned quadratic law: the triple cell grows at an accelerated rate (in comparison with the linear growth of the cells of mono-nature) and potentially reaches not the mass of $3 \cdot 243 \cdot \sqrt{4/\pi}$, but $3 \cdot 243 \cdot 4/\pi$. However, quadratic growth is also observed when an abstract independent particle exceeds the control mass of $243 \cdot 4/\pi$, which is quite content with one classitron cell.

It is important that with such behavior of the growth of any heavy particles, in the processes of fast quantum pumping of observation cells by equanta, the primary result will be the achievement of the coefficient of e-mass growth (in the System this is E_{ch}^2) of the mean-square, and not quadratic, value - as this is shown for the mass increase in the process of pumping by the integral $v^2/2$, within the limits from $v_1 = 1.11(1)$ to $v_2 = E_{2\alpha}$ of the relative velocity v of the absolute instantaneous growth of the e-mass of linear partons of any associate - a velocity proportional to the instantaneous relative value of this e-mass itself, in connection with which its numerical value, also relative, can be equated in calculations (as if geo-equivalently) to such a mass. For a conditionally unit starting mass of $1.11(1)^2$ and for any starting mass of the process $M_0 \cdot 1.11(1)^2$, when expressing velocities in dimensionless units, we obtain:

$$23. M_{mid} = m_1^2 + \int_{v_1}^{v_2} v dv; m_1 = 1.11(1); v_1 = 1.11(1); v_2 = E_{2\alpha} = 1.127868...$$

$$24. M_{mid} = 1/2(m_1^2 + m_2^2) = 1.119521...^2; m_2 = E_{2\alpha} = 1.127868...$$

$$25. M_A = M_0 \cdot M_{mid};$$

where M_0 is the linear component of the total starting mass of the particle/associate, which

during the pumping process reached the quadratic mass $M_0 * 1.11(1)^2$ in the observation cell, taking the form of a new particle/associate (for the classitron $M_0 = 243$); M_{mid} is the resonance mass and resonance coefficient, or the growth coefficient of the unit linear mass of any observation parton during the quadratic growth of the heavy associate that includes it within the observed growth limits.

In general terms, the mass-energy growth in each individual contact observation cell can be imagined as follows. The C_{CL} cell of the $2\alpha-1$ classitron, related in size to its Compton wavelength, reaches the limit of its linear saturation, when expressed in conventional units of mass, not greater than $243\sqrt{2} > M_{CCL}\sqrt{\pi/2} = 243E_{2\alpha}\sqrt{\pi/2}$, while its boundaries do not go beyond the outlines of the wave body $243\sqrt{4/\pi}\sqrt{\pi/2}$. Accordingly, with its forced weighting to the limit of $243\sqrt{2}$, one of the necessary conditions for the synthesis of the linear monobody 243 within its boundaries would be achieved, since the wave body of the weighted particle would receive the required contracted boundaries at this moment.

After saturation to the linear mass limit $243\sqrt{4/\pi} = 274/196...$ the contents of the cell can grow only quadratically (in case of fast, conditionally explosive, growth – mean square), that is, providing any parton of the included associate, any random structures, as well as the total sum of partons, with the possibility of increasing their mass also in the second dimension of their local time-space. Let us follow the development of the situation in the region of the growth sphere that interests us most, for the included speculative particle 243 as a component of the speculative particle of the linear type, the associate of partons 274,196....

Particle 243 now grows quadratically. At the moment when the growth coefficient reaches the value of $1.11(1)^2$ for the starting particle of the future alpha process $243 * 1.11(1)^2$, the conditions dictated by the spin-wave rule of the LOM are achieved, with a cascade coefficient of $1.11(1)$. In this case, the linear part of the emass of the cell 274.196 is represented, first, by the allocated emass 270, which has a special stability to be an independent associate or participant in a complex resonance, so that the particle $243 * 1.11(1)^2$ is isolated at least virtually into a separate body, and, second, by the residue of the mass, not greater than 4.192.... In this case, the linear part ($270 - 243 = 27$) of the allocated speculative mass $270 * 1.11(1)^2$, which previously occupied the sphere is displaced by the grown particle into the outer (contact) sphere in the form of partons with local masses $M_0 * 1.11(1)^2$. At this point, the process overcomes the plateau of stability “ $1.11(1)$ ”, that is, for some time during the formation of the starting particle of the alpha process “270”, the mean square rule does not operate within the framework of a kind of phase transition in the associate, but then again comes into its own.

The special stability of the 300/270/243 particle as the nucleus of the future alpha-associate 274.071... is connected first of all with the integerness of the partons organizing it both in the linear and in the quadratic component of the mass, and such partons become a kind of structural atoms, stratoms, of a new formation, quanta of its structure, and further growth of such a formation in any process of forced pumping does not lead to a change in the structure of the nucleus upon absorption of energy until Nature sees a new potential for integer addition into a whole of individual masses obeying the rules of the LOM. The stratomes of particle 270 have a mass one-third that of an electron and obey the spin-wave rule, but further, up to the hypothetical limiting mass of the linear contribution, less than 275, no suitable relationships are found linking the 243 stratoms of the classitron reaction cell into a similar large structure. The logical link explaining why Nature needs stratifications with special masses at all, in addition to the advantages of the same economy of thinking, should be discussed separately.

With further growth of the "starting alpha mass 270" with a total mass of $243 \cdot 1.11(1)^2$, the linear part of this mass gradually displaces more and more partons of the remainder 4.192... from the reaction sphere into the contact sphere, so that by the time the final plateau is reached, this linear part represents, according to the root-mean-square rule, the linear cross-section $243 \cdot E_{ch}$ of the total quadratic mass $243 \cdot E_{ch}^2$ and two parton mass remainders, included and excluded from the limit $E_{2\alpha}$ of the linear growth of the start mass 243, that is, $243 \cdot (E_{2\alpha} - E_{ch}) = 2.028380...$ and the second, with a mass of about $0.124... = 243\sqrt{4/\pi} - 243E_{2\alpha}$, in total – with a mass slightly greater than 2.1, if we do not count the quadratic one not taken into account here component, increasing such emass by E_{ch} times.

At this stage, the total material balance of the system is limited by the number $243 \cdot \sqrt{4/\pi} \cdot E_{ch}^2 > 243V^2$, i.e. it overcomes the requirements of the Compton-wave rule with its constant $\sqrt{4/\pi}$. The linear part of the total emass of the process is represented by the associate $243 \cdot E_{ch}$ (with the total mass $M_{01} \cdot E_{ch}^2$) and the undisplaced residues shown above, and the contact sphere is filled with partons with N resonant emasses $M_{0N} \cdot E_{ch}^2$ with the linear contribution to this mass still $M_{0N} \cdot E_{ch}$. Thus, an associate with an e-mass of $243 \cdot E_{2\alpha} E_{ch} = 2\alpha^{-1} \cdot E_{ch}$ gets the opportunity, when successful cascade proposals appear to form new connections of its e-mass growth, to capture the partons of the proposal that are missing from its needs, forming new cascade structures. It was noted above that its needs are met by an associate of partons with a total mass of $1/3 E_{ch}^2$ or, if we make balances and proportions only for the linear components according to condition (1) of the System, an associate of $1/3 E_{ch} = 1/3 \cdot 1.119521...$

From the contact sphere (parametrically distorted, as the wave body is compressed, into some mass-quadraticity, quasi-volume, which is not reflected in the calculations) for this reason a parton is captured in the form of an associate with a mass of $1/3 \cdot (1.119521...)^2$, but in the presence of close contact of cells, if the three components of the fusion 270, $(4 + 0.373173...)$ and $0.071998...$ of the cascade mass $274.445171...$, entering into interaction, belong to different cells, along with the unifying synthesis of an electron from three partons (the energy density required for synthesis remained sufficient in the entire contact body, not only in the sphere "243"), the partons 270 contained in the cells (under certain conditions) also enter into unifying cascade-cross bonds, which are simplified by the formula-proportion $810/270/90$ with a cascade coefficient of 3. Such a linear triumvirate-associate in this case acts as a potential target for the decay process of the alpha-triumvirate $3 \cdot (243 \cdot E_{2\alpha} + 1/3 E_{ch})$, and in view of the triple convergence of the cells, the single body synthesized from three suitable partons with certain spins gets the opportunity to be released during the decomposition of the structure of the resulting quasi-neutron with the formation of an independent electron body and inevitable fragments. The release occurs in a cell with the dimensions of the synthesis sphere "243", since this is the last linear mass in the representable series, still capable of fitting into a spherical body, ideally inscribed in a special cell of the flat parametric space " $243 \cdot \sqrt{4/\pi}$ ", therefore the electron as a triple body is endowed with a smaller relative mass of 1 (as $243/N^0$, and not $1.119521...$), and the wave body of the triumvirate collapses within the framework of the correspondence of the Compton wavelength to its new mass 810, throwing out the electron and fragments.

The quasi-neutron of metaphysics plays the role of a kind of electron boson, unknown to physics due to the difficulty of its detection and the difficulties of supersymmetry caused by this.

Why, according to condition (1) of the System, the partons of three cells are combined, and not the partons of each cell separately, is explained by the spin (or conditionally spin for imperfect associates) rule of merging three independent particles, reminiscent of the requirements of a gear

transmission:

The angular momenta of three particles merging into a new whole are initially represented by spins of both possible signs.

In this case, the associative content of each cell as a product of chaotic quantum pumping before the start of observing cross interactions can be imagined as a parton sum characterized by spins, or a common spin, of one sign, just as the rule of rotation of coaxial gears would require. Accordingly, three cells with both spin signs in a common set come together and then interact, and all the partons included by them also interact with each other.

The triple structure of the electron becomes the reason that does not allow it to be synthesized in the contact body of one classitron. Thus, we can imagine the physical, and not parametric, cell of the alpha process as a contact sphere with a linear capacity of potential, but not yet realized placement in it of an emass no greater than $243\sqrt{4/\pi} \cdot \sqrt{\pi/2} = 274.196... \cdot \sqrt{\pi/2} = 243\sqrt{2}$, which includes the reaction sphere of potentially realized placement of an emass of $243\sqrt{\pi/2}$, in which, in turn, a particle with an emass of 243 is synthesized or a triple particle with a unit electron mass corresponding to it in hidden energy expenditures of the t-machine of the universe. The problems of organization and conservation of charge, it should be clearly stipulated, are not considered here yet.

SUMMARY

Briefly generalizing and singling out the leading and guiding elements from the details of the thought experiment, it is worth mentioning first of all that when a certain definitely differentiated sum of masses in a certain observed volume – which can be distinguished by a special generalizing feature of being part of the linear component of the total mass-energy content of this volume – reaches the exact value of $3 \cdot 2\alpha^{-1} + E_{ch}$, in three converging spheres that make up this volume, called contact spheres by certain features and containing at that moment, as part of this sum, the main skeletal mass of $3 \cdot (270 + 4 + m_3)$ and three virtual particles with masses each of $1/3 E_{ch} = 1/3 ((E_{02} + E_{2\alpha^2}) / 2)^{1/2} = 1.119521061.../3$, conditions ripen for a new interaction, permitted by a separate rule of the Law of Organization of the Masses of the Universe. Thanks to this Cascade rule of LOM, the last of the above-mentioned three internal particles of the speculative volume, as elements of its general energy content, previously displaced from the reaction sphere of the experiment into the contact sphere, allow individual partons of the triumvirate to enter into a new cross-interaction with each other due to compliance with the requirements of the rule defined as the spin-wave condition of LOM (condition (1) of the System). The proportion established by the condition facilitates the formation of new particles from elements held together by bonds called cascade at the moment of their occurrence.

At the same time, however, three “ $1/3M_{ch}$ ”-particles captured by the common triple system of partons gain the potential to merge into one with the loss of part of the mass, because at this moment the local region of such a merger acquires a size (related to the classical radius of the electron; the quantum pump provided the necessary material compactification of each cell and any of its isolated regions by increasing its mass-energy density) corresponding to a reliable coordinate completion by the Counter of all minimal quanta of the future spherical electron body within the limits thus outlined, but not of quanta of any greater triple emass, and thus the electron for the first time gains the opportunity (within the framework of the process considered here) to become a completely coordinate-defined,

three-dimensional for physics – since also in the sense that all m-points of its structure become three-dimensionally completed – body.

Mathematically, this Compton condition for the upcoming electron synthesis is expressed by the inequality

$$26. \quad 243\sqrt{4/\pi} \geq 243\sqrt{2}/E_{ch}^2,$$

which tells us that the dimensions of the contact body corresponding to the electron synthesis cell with the conditional marker "243", due to the limits imposed by the Counter's speed, must be limited from above by the parameters of the reaction body of a particle weighted (in a linear expression) by $\sqrt{4/\pi}$ times, regardless of the conditions capable of ensuring this correspondence, and the task of the universe is to find such conditions by simple enumeration. Thus, a decrease in the volume of the wave body of a particle of a certain special mass, as it turned out, due to the concomitant reduction in the Compton wavelength of this particle, is an acceptable path to the success of the desired synthesis.

The milestones of this path are inevitably supplemented by some complications of a simple idea, to which even an anthropomorphic universe can afford to remain indifferent due to the fundamental trust in the reliable mechanistic nature of work on the experimental field of omnipresent quasi-randomness, and the tripling of the energies required for promising processes on the path of enumeration of options does not have the status of pretentiousness with which the universe could be puzzled.

The origin of various limits that establish parameters for special cells, and the very specialness of such cells find a detailed explanation in the Theory and are not considered here as factors that do not affect the course of calculation.

The question remains open at what exact moment the birth of an electron by fusion occurs, since the wave body of a quasi-neutron necessarily collapses after tripling under the Compton rule, and electron synthesis can occur at any stage of this compression, including the starting stage or, on the contrary, at the moment of the beginning of the parton tripling reaction 270 as a powerful Le Chatelier factor. Physics can be offered several options for consideration up to the achievement by the skeletal mass of the future triumvirate of the limiting cascade proportion $3(243E_{2\alpha}^2/243E_{2\alpha}/243)$ instead of the incomplete alpha proportion $243E_{2\alpha}E_{ch}/243E_{2\alpha}/(243 E_{2\alpha}/E_{ch})$, but here metaphysics, having established for itself the resulting numbers that finalize all moves, may not invade the adjacent diocese of the scientific hierarchy of plots.

As a result, a kind of undersaturation of partons of the potential alpha triumvirate, born from mass-energy clots, leads to the capture from contact spheres as special spatial cells of the partons missing for the new cascade ratio of masses $1/3 E_{ch}$ from condition (1) of the System, and to the subsequent entry into new cross-links with the formation of an unstable complex particle of a quasi-neutron, after which the electron synthesized in parallel - due to the suitable cell size - gets the opportunity to emerge into an independent existence as a result of the decay of the quasi-neutron in one of the channels in the direction of the known target $3*270$ with the formation in potential of either this particle, or some particles of intermediate mass in the case of a quasi-random generation in the channel of new cross-links, or a number of smaller fragments.

Strengthening the ontological emphasis, we can repeat that the parameters of the electron's

tabular mass are determined by the speed of the t-machine of the universe, which we call the Counter, which allows for a complete calculation, that is, in fact, the existence of an electron, precisely such a defined tabular, because the limiting, mass within the boundaries of a strictly defined special volume, which is also a physical constant of the universe, if this limiting mass belongs to a triple, three-parton, body of the electron type and belongs to the category of linear masses according to the classification of the Law of Organization of Masses of the Universe.

The statement of the three-parton structure of any body (specifying logically strictly), if it motivates the establishment of its mass, refers only to the moment of its synthesis in some process, and is not obligatory for further existence in the case of some restructuring of the internal structure, which can lead to both simplification and to an energetically advantageous complication of this structure. In this regard, the structural features of the acting, and not synthesized, electron are not discussed in this article.

By resorting to the aid of auxiliary coefficients to the coordination of the form-generating volumes of different geometries, in our case – the countable parametric and physical ones – the universe faced the problem of coordinating the frequent spherical requirements of physics with the flat propositions of the Countable space. The complexity of the problem was increased by the natural limitation of the speed of its t-machine, but it is precisely to the specific solutions of all such problems that the physics of the universe owes all the subtleties of its laws and the values of its constants, and there are no other reasons for their precise formation, not excluding randomness or variability pure from hidden regularities from the list of unnecessary things.

All universes of the Multiverse are guided by the same complete set of their laws and constants and are legislatively identical.

In physical space, the cube of metaphysical time-space is not a cube, a plane is not a plane, two-dimensionality and six-dimensionality are not two-dimensionality and six-dimensionality, but no complicating circumstances are capable of preventing the observer from accurately establishing quantities of any nature on the paths of unifying the views of physics and ontologically constructed natural philosophy, for these circumstances are finite, which puts an end to the old dispute about the cognizability of the universe formally-logically.

Thus, the concentration of abstract mass-energy in a certain limited volume upon reaching the locally necessary critical density allows in some cases (we omit here the study of types of energy) to obtain stable objects of the microworld at the output at the moment this energy reaches its equivalent mass, determined in linear or quadratic calculation by a value suitable for organizing new cross-links between interaction partons, also taking into account the number of neighboring spatial cells of the physical space of the universe included in the process. The special feature of these cells is most often the borderline of their sizes in relation to certain aspects of the ability of the universe to pack in such volumes corporeal masses that obey the laws of quadratic or linear arrangement.

Let us note in the margins that a direct comparison of the properties or causal series of a purely speculative quasi-neutron from the alpha process considered here and the neutrons of physics is impossible; the ontology of the natural neutron presents an additional problem.

The sizes of special cells have no relation to the calibration of any field or to the admissible lattice approximation of it, their size is determined by other factors, their existence depends on the conditions of instantaneous observation and does not extend to low-energy zones of world space, and,

in essence, by its nature is short-term, secondary, globally non-local and physically not assumed.

In the described quasi-random way, the physics of the universe fixes for itself the relationship between the Compton wavelength of the electron, in the usual way inversely linearly related to its instantaneous, for time-space, mass, and the wavelength of the virtual cubic body of the classitron of physics - the halved classitron of metaphysics - the mass of which obeys, albeit virtually, the general rules of the LOM, and the three-dimensional material body of the electron is geometrically inscribed in the cell determined for the Compton wavelength of the classitron in the parametric space of the metaphysical Counter of the states of the universe, its t-machine.

It should not be forgotten that the detailed physics of the process is drawn in nuances, and its metaphysics, not physics, was subject to consideration; mandatory figures of relationships between the parameters of its participants were revealed, not mandatory stages or optional figures - they were revealed in a special way, preceding physics, not revealing it. Physical labyrinths of specific materializations of any processes are not capable, however, of changing the quantitative establishments of scientific metaphysics as a physical ontology, changing the basic requirements dictated by the simple geometry of the spatial substrate for the placement of all that exists (or speculative), imposed on procedural actors under the guise of a set of laws of the most fundamental property. The metaphysics of processes is therefore far from their entire physics and provides scenes from a film rather than the film itself, a kind of cutting of the most striking or significant frames from a full-length film for presentation to its observers who have not yet had the opportunity to get into a movie theater.

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**GLOSSARY

1. We will call scientific, or quantitative, metaphysics, or in the context of this article simply

metaphysics, a section of fundamental physics devoted to the identification of hidden patterns of the universe, included in the hierarchy of physical laws as primary, and discursively based on the deductive impulse in the study of logical patterns that can lead to such identification and its subsequent verification. Let us begin with the terminological, temporarily outlined only by the goals of this article and not legalized more widely, propaedeutics of the locally proposed here metaphysical approach with an emphasis only on categories that can receive in metaphysics some special sound or shades of such, not characteristic of physics, or the origin of which may differ from ideas about similar processes in physics.

2. We shall call *emass* the total rest energy of any phenomenon observed in local space, regardless of the quality and classification of the types of observed energy, expressed by means of a direct and simple interpretation of Einstein equivalence and being the sum of partonic or quantized masses and included energies of the phenomenon – a sum expressed in some conventional units, and in the framework of this article, for further simplification, in units of electron mass.

3. We shall call particles independent bodies of the microworld that meet all the rules of the Law of Organization of Masses of the Universe and, in connection with this, demonstrate original properties and signs of existence that are fundamentally detected by the physics of the universe.

4. We shall call “associates” short-term, resonantly or virtually existing bodies, a type of quasi-particles that meet one, or an incomplete list, of the rules of the Law of Organization of Masses of the Universe and that have received in this connection some isolated existence that does not necessarily show properties or evidence of existence that are determined by physics. The simplest particular example is the possible absence of wave properties and the impossibility of finding in space any correspondence that could be associated with the Compton wavelength of a quasi-particle. An associate can also be considered a short-lived particle, about which the observer is not physically sure whether it meets all the rules of the LOM, which is caused by the imperfection or fundamental absence of the available tools. In this sense, it is permissible to use the concept of an associate more generally, as a synonym for the concept of “particle” when considering processes in which a reliable division of objects into the above-mentioned categories is difficult or of no particular importance.

5. A spherical particle will be any particle endowed with an angular momentum and capable of inscribing all material quanta, or *m*-points, of its mass-energy body into a certain idealized sphere of rotation in the dynamics of its conditional rest. Precessing spindles in this sense will also be classified as spherical particles.

6. According to the classification of the Law of Organization of Masses in Metaphysics, linear particles will be independent bodies with a reduced Compton wavelength not less than half the length of the classical radius of an electron. Particles with a smaller reduced wavelength will be called quadratic. In ideally identical conditions of the eventual mass-energy growth proposed to the particles, with the organization of the corresponding influx of energy (or instantly delivered saturation density) into the reaction volume, quadratic particles reach large masses and grow instantaneously faster than linear ones in the ratio indicated by their names. We are talking about speculative or some particles that are really capable of such growth and suitable for comparison in the experiment.

7. Let us call *geo-equivalence* a correspondence that allows, when choosing one of the possible principles of packing *emass* into volumes, to express some dimensional parameters of volumes in dimensionless units of *emass*. Linear bodies allow using such a correspondence for linear measurements

of volume - for radii, side lengths or some specific characteristic length, quadratic - for areas, cubic - for volumes. Geo-equivalence is limitedly admissible for special cases of microcosm bodies or as a phase in the full cycle of their synthesis, and for emasses far from reaching the density parameters of black holes in the observed volume.

8. Let us call a parametric cell of the synthesis of a spherical particle of three-dimensional space a cubic volume with a side of 2, describing the sphere of a particle with a radius of 1, structurally absorbing all of its energy mass (or half-mass in a special case of observation) without a remainder.

9. Let us call a contact sphere or an associative sphere of a particle a spherical volume whose projection circle on the observation plane corresponds to the equation

$$27. \quad x^2 + y^2 = R_c^2,$$

where x and y take independent values from 0 to $\sqrt{2}$, while x at the same time corresponds to the geo-equivalent half-mass of the linear contribution to the emass of the observed particle in the same range from 0 to $\sqrt{2}$. Moving away from the zero value and taking as a unit, as an example, the half-mass $243/2$ of such a particle with an emass of 243, we arrive at the value of the radius of the contact sphere of maximum $(243/2)*\sqrt{2}$, that is, at the value of its diameter $243*\sqrt{2}$ and at the corresponding potential of linear filling of the sphere with an equivalent emass content.

10. Let us call the reaction or packing sphere of a particle, the synthesis sphere or the calculation sphere the spherical volume quantitatively equal to the volume of the parametric cell, the projection circle of which on the observation plane corresponds to the equation

$$28. \quad x^2 + y^2 = R_s^2 = R_c^2 / (\pi/2)$$

11. Let us call the contact and packing spheres of a linear particle or associate according to the LOM classification the spherical volumes described by the projection circle on the observation plane corresponding to the equation, respectively

$$29. \quad C_{Rc}^2 = R_c^2 \text{ и}$$

$$30. \quad C_{Rs}^2 = R_s^2 = R_c^2 / (\pi/2);$$

$$31. \quad C_{Ls}^2 = L_s^2 = R_c^2 / \sqrt{2} = R_s^2 / (4/\pi),$$

where C is the packing geo-equivalent of the e-half-mass of the associate as, respectively, the contact radius R_c , the calculated radius R_s and the half-length L_s of the side of its parametric cube (PC) in the Countable time-space; R_s also serves as the half-length of the side of the conditional parametric cube in space-time - a cube that theoretically contains linearly packed e-mass greater by $(4/\pi)^{1/2}$ times than the sphere of synthesis allows within the framework of its geo-equivalence (for example, for the e-mass 243), which is convenient for a quick assessment of the ratios of the capacity of parametric and physical spaces, having at hand only data on the lengths of Compton waves in physics.

12. As an example, we note the following expressions that are useful when considering speculative particles with certain masses of the linear contribution x to the total half-mass (in this case, replaced by its equivalent - the half-length of the side of the PC):

32. $x^2 + y^2 = R_c^2 = (E_{ch} * \sqrt{2})^2$ для $x = y = E_{ch}$;
 33. $x^2 + y^2 = R_c^2 = (E_{2a} * \sqrt{2})^2$ для $x = y = E_{2a}$;
 34. $x^2 + y^2 = R_c^2 = (E_{ch} * \sqrt{2})^2$ для $x = 1,11(1)$; $y = E_{2a}$.

The last expression can be illustratively useful in the case when particles that meet the condition $R_c^2 = (E_{ch} * \sqrt{2})^2$ can have different structures in the parametric space, in particular, as regards the ratio of the shares of the quadratic and linear contributions to the total mass, or when under certain conditions a particle or associate of one structure can be rebuilt into an object of another structure or into its own isomer, and in the first case it can change the total mass with the absorption or alienation of excess mass in the form of fragments - and at the same time a number of semi-virtual particles of different masses at some phase of the process can have the same size contact sphere. This process can be reversible or even ideally reversible, that is, it is possible to observe a case of resonating masses. More probable, in the general number of cases, is the variant of symmetrization of quadratic masses obeying the spin-wave rule of LOM, when the determining factor should be considered the standardization by the Counter, other things being equal or unimportant, the principle of economy of thinking, however, in the case of ideal resonance, the decisive factor will be the intervention of the Le Chatelier principle and the side processes adequate to it under the observed conditions.

13. The above expressions did not take into account the fact that large particles with masses greater than $243(4/\pi)^{1/4}$ cannot have wave bodies whose radius exceeds $243\sqrt{2}$ (which characterizes the body of a boundary classitron for the LOM), so we were talking about abstract examples or about some associates with such masses, for which the size of wave bodies is insignificant. It can be assumed that the initial contact body of the associate, when it is transformed into a particle, collapses its dimensions to those permitted by the LOM at the second stage of its own synthesis, and the corresponding part of the mass, which was taken as a share of the linear contact mass at the first stage, goes into a quadratic state in exactly the same proportion as the radius of the contact body is reduced relative to the classical radius of the electron, with the transition of the body to a wave state (part of the half-masses, when looking at things physically, goes from the observed base of the cylindrical section of the local solid torus into the depths of its half-spaces).

14. A genetically important parameter for heavy associates is the packing radius. At this radius, one should monitor the achievement by the packing sphere of the energy density necessary as a primary condition of the LOM for the synthesis of a possible particle. In this case, the parent contact body that exceeds this packing body in size and contains it can be considered responsible for achieving the above-mentioned density: its average mass-energy density should be the same.

15. It should not be overlooked that in cases where the parameters of the wave body of the forming associate act as a limitation for the dimensions of the contact body, it is necessary to take into account the reduction of the latter with the growth of mass, so that the observed e-density will grow quadratically with the change of the latter. It is possible to simplify the consideration, however, formally accepting the contact body as unchanged and only filling, like any abstract region, with a mass-energy growing with a quadratic coefficient. The coinciding conclusions for the resulting density of two mathematical variations will not have a decisive significance for physical calculations except for cases that prohibit such approximations, for example, as a result of complex intermediate transformations of

contact bodies into wave bodies and back directly in the process of observation.

16. Let us discard for the time being considerations associated with attempts to depict the alpha process more physically reliably than is required for the fastest calculation of constants. Remembering that the Counter performs calculations in two local half-spaces of the total bi-mass of an independent particle/associate separately for each of the hemispheres of the instant, we shall take as the starting calculation the half value of the pumping mass included in any parametric square of the time-space section of any of the two moments of one instant and corresponding to the packing of the total mass of the observed object in the full double instant of observation. Thus, the equation of the circle of the contact section of the object of observation, describing the parametric square, can be written using geo-equivalence - if the fact of direct proportionality of the units of the linearly packed dimensionless mass to the radius (in this case, not the diameter) of this sphere is obvious - replacing the geometric lengths on the coordinate axes with relative masses or growth coefficients of the latter during the observation time.

17. Taking the example of a classitron or an electron born in its volume (both are linear bodies), it is easy to see that both will require a quadratic growth of density relative to the starting one, corresponding to filling them with the emass of the entire contact region - only in this case will compliance with the requirement allow their linear density of the synthesis sphere to become equal to the linear density of the region. This conditionally quadratic growth of density with the coefficient $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ can be ensured either by the growth of the linear pre-packing of the region with the emass with the same coefficient, or by the reduction of the radius of the region, parallel to the growth, in the process of emass growth with the coefficient $(\pi/2)^{1/4}$.

18. Symmetrical compliance with the spin-wave rule of the LOM will be fulfilled in the general case with the corresponding selection, with the growth of the mass of any associate, in its linear body of also two growth zones, primary and secondary - related mass-energy so that the spin-wave rule of type (1) is fulfilled. The quadratic fraction of the mass inside the packing body in such a consideration can often be called tertiary, since the mentioned rule (1) requires three participants. For example, for a speculative particle 300, the primary mass will be 243, the secondary 27, and the tertiary 30.

19. The Counter operates in this case as if with blocks of structures. Thus, the particle 300 obtained in an alternative way, the Counter can consider as composed of blocks 270, 27 and 3, obeying the spin-wave rule $(270 + 27 + 3)/(27 + 3)/3$ and arising as a result of the growth evolution of particle 270 according to the rule $300/30/3$, so that the path of evolution itself has no decisive significance in the metaphysics of the organization of masses. The counter can operate with block 243 as the initial one, build it up to a mass of 270, and then, in the process of further mass growth, use – under certain special conditions, in an alien contact body, for example – one and the same linear coefficient for each dimension of the count, so that block 243 corresponds to block 270 and block 300 respectively for one, two, and three dimensions of the same count (dimensions that have no relation here to the dimensions of space, although in Nature the physical observation of such a relation is randomly permissible).

20. Particles symmetrical with respect to the spin-wave rule are distinguished by the equality of the primary and secondary linear coefficients of mass organization and definitely correspond better to the principle of economy of thought; the quadratic coefficient is then a simple square of the primary, and the primary and secondary cascade coefficients are equal. Of course, the observer should not assume the existence of true thinking in the Counter in natural universes, but explain the stability of

symmetric particles by other probabilistic considerations, for example, related to rotation and the complications brought to the Counter by this factor, calling for simplification.

21. Since in the 3-sphere of the universe the partons of each of the two signs of the half-mass of a whole particle formally belong to their own Clifford solid torus, and not to the entire 3-sphere, we can speak for speculative purposes and in a simplified manner about their location in a certain local packing sphere, which has, within the framework of its moment of existence, the shape of a simple cylinder, the axial section of which has the shape of an ideal circle with a radius geoequivalent for linear particles to their "packing half-mass". In this model we will place the half-mass of a linear property on the upper observable base of such a cylinder of a quasi-physical half-space, and the quadratic component of its mass - in its deep sections. Sic: in parametric space all components of emass belong to one section of the cylinder of each of the two moments in the common instant of time-space, which is not a requirement imposed on physics, in view of the appearance of "deep" distances only in the interaction of two modes of the time-space model proposed for use (in principle, there are four modes, the details of which can be temporarily omitted).

22. The 3-sphere, however, as a sum of solid-torus modes, purely geometrically has a radius $\sqrt{2}$ times greater, which corresponds to the radius of the contact, and not the packing, sphere of the particle (or future particle). Thus, in view of the temporal, and not purely spatial, distinction between solid-torus modes, we can speak, removing the contradiction, of the contact sphere of the particle as belonging to a bimodal space, and of the reaction sphere as belonging to a single-modal space. In this case, energetically compacting the contact sphere to a certain critical value, we compact the modal sections of solid tori to the density of each half-mass separately in each mode required by the synthesis conditions. As a result, the total reaction mass of the associate will be enclosed as if in a section of a parametric cube with a side length (for linear bodies) equivalent to the total mass of a speculative particle, and not to two half-masses as was the case in the single-mode consideration.

23. Returning to the doubling of the half-masses in the bi-mode of Counting - to the half-masses inscribed together in the considered contact sphere (the "mass-diameter" approximation), one should operate with the linear emass 243 for a spherical body in the parametric square of Counting and the linear emass $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$ in the sphere of synthesis for the associate inscribing the emass in the speculative square in physical space. If the density of $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$ emass per its size, determined by the classical radius of the electron, is reached in the synthesis sphere of "243", then one of the conditions of the ZOM for the synthesis of the electron mass or, optionally, the linear monomass of 243 will be fulfilled.

24. The synthesis zone of "243" is geometrically capable of including a linear associate with an emass of $243\sqrt{4/\pi} \sim 274.196$, but a spherical body with an emass of no more than 243. If the observer notices the saturation of a linearly organized region with greater energy, new portions of emass will fill the growth zone allowed by the quadratic rule, and as a whole the non-spherical associate can reach a mass of $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$. At each stage of growth, its mass will be determined by expression (28) for geoequivalent linear coordinates, each corresponding to its own growth coefficient for each of the two dimensions of the Account. Thus, for the contact sphere of a spherical particle 243 (or parametric associate $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$) at the start of the experiment), a linear distribution of mass 274.196 is characteristic over the entire parametric section of the contact body with a radius $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ times greater. In this case, the equivalent radius $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$ corresponds to the critical wavelength in physical space, which still

allows a linear form of packing of e-masses into volumes. At this radius, with the above-mentioned distribution of emass, a part of emass of $243\sqrt{4/\pi} / \sqrt{\pi/2}$ is observed, at the radius of $243\sqrt{4/\pi} * (\pi/2)^{1/4}$, a part of $243\sqrt{4/\pi} / (\pi/2)^{1/4}$ is allocated, and at the radius of $243\sqrt{2}$, the entire mass of $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$ is allocated.

25. At the last of the above-mentioned radii, with the connection of the quantum pump, we will theoretically increase the linear saturation by $(\pi/2)^{1/4}$ times, which is virtually permissible, since linear saturation with abstract energy occurs at this radius only when the emass parameter of the volume reaches a value of $(\pi/2)^{1/2}$ times greater. Let us note as a determining fact that each conditional quantum of mass-energy of a conditionally homogeneous saturation broth will increase the mass in this case by $(\pi/2)^{1/4}$ times. We can speak about the existence in the contact body of a certain virtual associate with a cascade coefficient of $(\pi/2)^{1/4} - 243\sqrt{4/\pi} * (\pi/2)^{1/4} / 243\sqrt{4/\pi} / 243\sqrt{4/\pi} / (\pi/2)^{1/4}$. With further operation of the quantum pump, we achieve the maximum linear saturation of the contact sphere $243\sqrt{4/\pi} * (\pi/2)^{1/2}$ on the same radius, and the cascade body is characterized by the formula $243\sqrt{4/\pi} * (\pi/2)^{1/2} / 243\sqrt{4/\pi} * (\pi/2)^{1/4} / 243\sqrt{4/\pi}$. However, if the contact body of the process falls within the dimensions of the wave body of the associate, then this contact body is forced to reduce its radius in proportion to the increase in the included mass, that is, with the same control coefficient $(\pi/2)^{1/2}$. Thus, in one of the wave spheres of this stage of the associative process, the entire mass of the contact body $243\sqrt{4/\pi} * (\pi/2)^{1/2}$ is included in a sphere with a radius of $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$ and is represented in this sphere by partons of masses with parton weights $N * (\pi/2)^{1/2}$, where N is the initial quantity in any object included in the region of conditional minimal quanta of the experiment at the moment of its beginning, or, in other units, the initial mass of this object.

26. Let us return to the beginning of the experiment and repeat it, this time observing the radius of the synthesis of $243E_{2a}$, smaller than the radius of $243\sqrt{4/\pi}$. The linear part of the mass at this smaller radius will be represented by the mass of $243E_{2a}$, the reaction volume will be filled with partons $N * (\pi/2)^{1/2}$, and in the case of a favorable ratio of parton masses, it is possible to organize some new cascade bodies with the participation of the linear and quadratic parts of the masses included in the broth, which we presumably do not observe.

27. Let us return to the beginning of the experiment again and repeat it with the coefficient of linear saturation E_{ch}^2 , exceeding the geometric coefficient $(\pi/2)^{1/2}$. The radius of synthesis $243\sqrt{2} / E_{ch}^2 \sim 274.196$ is to be observed, the linear part of the mass 274.196 of the reaction sphere of which will include the mass $243E_{2a} \sim 274.072$ as the largest of its components and will be supplemented in the synthesis sphere by partons $N * E_{ch}$. This reaction sphere has a linear capacity, at the time of observation, $274.196 > 243E_{2a}$, but the linear density of the virtual synthesis sphere $243E_{2a}$ included in it already allows one to overcome the density threshold required for the synthesis of an electron or its energy monoisomer as a primary condition, since the compression coefficient E_{ch}^2 exceeded the compression coefficient $(\pi/2)^{1/2}$ along the entire linear length of the contact sphere $243\sqrt{2}$.

28. Next, the process of cascade synthesis is set in motion based on virtual particles $N * E_{ch}^2$ (more precisely, $1/3 * E_{ch}^2$ in this case) and the linear contribution of 274.072 in the composition of the mass $274.072 * E_{ch}$ (formally – $(274.072/E_{ch}) * E_{ch}^2$), reflected by expression (1), with the output of a quasi-neutron and the final emission of an electron as a natural maximum in a series of triple linear masses allowed to exist in a special cell of the universal space – in a sphere with a diameter equal to the diameter of the classical radius of an electron.

29. Briefly summarizing, it can be noted that with the transformation of the quantum soup of virtual pumping into the associate " $243E_{2a} * E_{CH}^2$ ", the special wave body of the observed speculative particle is compressed according to the Compton requirement by E_{CH}^2 times, but such a diametrical shrinkage of the contact cell means its transformation into a reaction cell, which launches the above-mentioned processes due to the satisfaction of the corresponding density energy requirements of the LOM.

30. In the "spherical" (in the modus - cylindrical) part of the reaction volume $N * \sqrt{4/\pi} * E_{CH}^2$, containing in itself a $\sqrt{4/\pi}$ smaller mass $N * E_{CH}^2$, we can observe a temporary equilibrium of resonances with a material balance $N * E_{CH}^2$, supported by different virtual objects with different parameters x and y from expression (28), including the options $x = E_{CH}$, $y = E_{CH}$; $\{x = E_{2a}, y = 1.11(1)\} + \Delta m$; $(x = 1.11(1), y = E_{2a}) + \Delta m$; $\{x = 1.11(1), y = 1.11(1)\} + \Delta m$, so that the virtual linear particle $243 * 1.11(1)$ and a significant participant in the alpha cascade 270 can become an element of the alpha process on completely legal grounds as an object with an acceptable mass, the existence of which in resonances is provoked by geometric prerequisites.

31. It is also useful to pay attention to the consequence of the six-dimensionality of the Counting space, which leads to the establishment of the value of the mass m_3 of the cross cascade in the amount of one third of the electron mass, when $N^D = 729$. The formation of such a particle can be entrusted to a simple associative probability, but one can also assume its preliminary formation in a quantum soup from a three-parton embryo, which has as a linear fraction of the mass that constitutes it, the skeletal mass of $1/3$ (that is, $243/729$). In this case, the idea that the universe uses this mass when starting the alpha reaction as a single one, as a counting quantum, also receives additional arguments, and that the integerness of the mass number 270 (or, when expressed in these quanta, 810) acquires some locally sacred meaning: in fact, the center of the computational interests of the entire computational work of the t-machine was the particle " $1/3$ ", and not the total mass 243 applied to it, and the development of which it was proposed here to especially monitor.